

A Brief Review of Orbital Equations Using Matrices

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Abstract

The derivation of the basic differential equations used to describe the motion of a satellite in orbit around a gravitating central mass is usually presented in customary vector notation. In contrast to this, a slightly different approach is provided here. We derive these equations for three dimensional orbital motion by way of rotation matrices, with little additional comment.

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1 Central Force Motion

In two dimensional orbit theory, we usually first consider the central mass to be infinite, with a *point* mass rotating around it. The center mass is either a *point* mass or spherical. After that, we let the "central mass" have any arbitrary value, with the center of rotation specified by the center of mass (CM). Since there are only two point masses and the attractive (or repulsive) force is a central force, the motion is planar, and the position of the rotating mass can be specified by polar coordinates (r, θ) . There is only one angle necessary, and that is theta. The angle theta is the angle of the pole, r , relative to the x-axis.

There are two angles that are necessary to specify the position of a point in three dimensional space, theta and phi. These two angles specify the angular position of the pole, R . This situation contrasts with rigid body theory, in which *three* angles, θ , ϕ and ψ are necessary for specification of the positions of the rotating mass particle(s). Again, the two angles $\theta(t)$ and $\phi(t)$ specify the angular position of the pole R , but in addition, the angle ψ specifies the positions of point mass particles rotating around that same pole. We do not examine rigid body motion in this paper.

1.1 The Three Dimensional Coordinate Frame

Consider a position vector $\mathbf{R}$ of a point P in a Cartesian coordinate system, the Laboratory System S with (space-axes) coordinates x, y, z .

Figure1: Two Coordinate Systems

For spherical coordinates, R, θ, ϕ ,

$$\begin{cases} x = r \cos \theta = R \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ y = r \sin \theta = R \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ z = R \cos \phi \\ r = R \sin \phi \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = R \begin{pmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

are the coordinates of a point P in the laboratory system (the primary or base system).

1.1.1 Coordinate Transformations in 3D

Suppose that we make a copy of the laboratory coordinate system S and rotate it in the following manner.

Remember, we are transforming components of a vector to a rotated coordinate system, that is, we are rotating the coordinate system, *not* the vector.

$$1^{st} \text{ rotation: } \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \\ z_1 \end{pmatrix} = Z(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where } Z(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

and

$$2^{nd} \text{ rotation: } \begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = Y(\phi) \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \\ z_1 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where } Y(\phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi & 0 & -\sin \phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = Y(\phi) \cdot Z(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where x, y, z are coordinates in the laboratory system (the primary or basic frame), and x', y', z' are coordinates in the coordinate system obtained after two rotations, $Z(\theta)$ and $Y(\phi)$. $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{i}x + \mathbf{j}y + \mathbf{k}z$ is the vector expressed in terms of *the laboratory system* of coordinates. $\mathbf{R}'$ is the same vector expressed in terms of coordinates in the coordinate system obtained after these same two rotations. Customarily, only one vector symbol is used for vectors, e.g., $\mathbf{R}$, regardless of which system the coordinate components are expressed. However, in this paper we elect to use two symbols, $\mathbf{R}$ and $\mathbf{R}'$, with $\mathbf{R}' = \mathbf{R}$.

$$\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{i}x + \mathbf{j}y + \mathbf{k}z, \quad \mathbf{R}' = (\mathbf{e}_\phi, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_R) \begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{e}_\phi x' + \mathbf{e}_\theta y' + \mathbf{e}_R z'$$

We may at times use the following (suggestive) alias if convenient:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_\phi \\ y_\theta \\ z_R \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix}$$

$S(\theta, \phi)$ is the coordinate transformation matrix relating the components of position vector $\mathbf{R}'$ in the rotated coordinate system S' to the components of $\mathbf{R}$ in the laboratory coordinate system S .

$$S(\theta, \phi) = Y(\phi) \cdot Z(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi & 0 & -\sin \phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S(\theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \sin \theta & -\sin \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ \sin \phi \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_\phi \\ y_\theta \\ z_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \sin \theta & -\sin \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ \sin \phi \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) = S^T(\theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix}$$

Taking the (total) time derivative of $\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$, we have...

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \dot{R} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} + R \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \cos \phi \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \dot{R} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} + R \sin \phi \dot{\theta} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + R \dot{\phi} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= \dot{R} \sin \phi \cos \theta + R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \dot{y} &= \dot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta + R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \dot{z} &= \dot{R} \cos \phi - R \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \end{aligned}$$

or, rearranging terms,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \dot{R} \cos \phi \cos \theta \\ \dot{y} &= R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \dot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \dot{z} &= -R \dot{\phi} \sin \phi + 0 + \dot{R} \cos \phi \end{aligned}$$

that is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} R \dot{\phi} \\ R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{pmatrix} \stackrel{D}{=} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R \dot{\phi} \\ R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} = S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R \dot{\phi} \\ R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix}$$

where

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} \stackrel{D}{=} \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

are velocity components along $\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_\phi \\ y_\theta \\ z_R \end{pmatrix}$, that is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{pmatrix} = S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v^2 &= \dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2 + \dot{z}^2 = (\dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}) \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \left[S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \right]^T \left[S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \right] \\ &= \left[(R\dot{\phi}, R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi, \dot{R}) S(\theta, \phi) \right] \left[S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \right] \\ &= \dot{R}^2 + (R\dot{\theta}\sin\phi)^2 + (R\dot{\phi})^2 \\ v^2 &= v_R^2 + v_\theta^2 + v_\phi^2 = \dot{R}^2 + R^2\dot{\theta}^2\sin^2\phi + R^2\dot{\phi}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

For later use,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{S}(\theta, \phi) &= \dot{\theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} S(\theta, \phi) + \dot{\phi} \frac{d}{d\phi} S(\theta, \phi) \\ \dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) &= \dot{\theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} S^T(\theta, \phi) + \dot{\phi} \frac{d}{d\phi} S^T(\theta, \phi) \end{aligned}$$

Computing the derivatives and simplifying, we have...

$$\dot{S}(\theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{\theta} \cos\phi \sin\theta - \dot{\phi} \sin\phi \cos\theta & -\dot{\theta} \cos\theta & -\dot{\theta} \sin\phi \sin\theta + \dot{\phi} \cos\phi \cos\theta \\ \dot{\theta} \cos\phi \cos\theta - \dot{\phi} \sin\phi \sin\theta & -\dot{\theta} \sin\theta & \dot{\theta} \sin\phi \cos\theta + \dot{\phi} \cos\phi \sin\theta \\ -\dot{\phi} \cos\phi & 0 & -\dot{\phi} \sin\phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) = \left[\dot{S}(\theta, \phi) \right]^T \equiv \frac{d}{dt} S^T(\theta, \phi)$$

$$\dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta - \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \cos \theta & \dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta - \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \sin \theta & -\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \\ -\dot{\theta} \cos \theta & -\dot{\theta} \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta & \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta & -\dot{\phi} \sin \phi \end{pmatrix}$$

1.1.2 Unit Vectors in 3D

Suppose that in the second of Eqs.(8), we perform the following replacements:

$$x \leftarrow \mathbf{i}, \quad y \leftarrow \mathbf{j}, \quad z \leftarrow \mathbf{k} \quad \text{and} \quad x_\phi \leftarrow \mathbf{e}_\phi, \quad x_\theta \leftarrow \mathbf{e}_\theta, \quad x_R \leftarrow \mathbf{e}_R.$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_\phi \\ \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ \mathbf{e}_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \sin \theta & -\sin \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ \sin \phi \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \end{pmatrix}$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_\phi &= \mathbf{i} \cos \phi \cos \theta + \mathbf{j} \cos \phi \sin \theta - \mathbf{k} \sin \phi \\ \mathbf{e}_\theta &= -\mathbf{i} \sin \theta + \mathbf{j} \cos \theta \\ \mathbf{e}_R &= \mathbf{i} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \mathbf{j} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The first of Eqs(8), repeated below

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_R \\ v_\theta \\ v_\phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{R} \\ R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ R \dot{\phi} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ \cos \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix}$$

is the three-dimensional counterpart of

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_r \\ v_\theta \end{pmatrix} = Z(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \end{pmatrix}$$

1.1.3 The Acceleration Vector

Likewise,

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix} &= \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} \right] = \frac{d}{dt} \left[S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R \dot{\phi} \\ R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Taking the time derivative of $\begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{pmatrix}$ we obtain

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix} \stackrel{D}{=} \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} + S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} \dot{v}_\phi \\ \dot{v}_\theta \\ \dot{v}_R \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_\phi \\ a_\theta \\ a_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

This equation relates the acceleration vectors in the two coordinate systems, S and S' .

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_\phi \\ a_\theta \\ a_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \left[\dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} + S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} \dot{v}_\phi \\ \dot{v}_\theta \\ \dot{v}_R \end{pmatrix} \right], \text{ that is,}$$

$$\boxed{\begin{pmatrix} a_\phi \\ a_\theta \\ a_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} v_\phi \\ v_\theta \\ v_R \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \dot{v}_\phi \\ \dot{v}_\theta \\ \dot{v}_R \end{pmatrix}} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_\phi \\ a_\theta \\ a_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \dot{S}^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \dot{R}\dot{\phi} + R\ddot{\phi} \\ \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi + R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi + R\dot{\theta}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \\ \ddot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x &= r \cos \theta = R \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ y &= r \sin \theta = R \sin \phi \sin \theta \quad , \quad r = R \sin \phi \\ z &= R \cos \phi \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= \dot{R} \sin \phi \cos \theta + R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \dot{y} &= \dot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta + R \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \dot{z} &= \dot{R} \cos \phi - R \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = S^{-1}(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} = S^T(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \left[\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \right] \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix} \\ + \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta - \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \cos \theta & -\dot{\theta} \cos \theta & -\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta - \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \sin \theta & -\dot{\theta} \sin \theta & \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta \\ -\dot{\phi} \cos \phi & 0 & -\dot{\phi} \sin \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} R\dot{\phi} \\ R\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \dot{R} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta & \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{R}\dot{\phi} + R\ddot{\phi} \\ \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi + R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi + R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \\ \ddot{R} \end{pmatrix} \\
\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} & = \begin{pmatrix} -R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta \\ R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta + \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta \\ -R\dot{\phi}^2 \cos \phi - \dot{R}\dot{\phi} \sin \phi \end{pmatrix} \\
& + \begin{pmatrix} \dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta - R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + \dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ -\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \sin \phi - R\ddot{\phi} \sin \phi + \ddot{R} \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \\
& = \begin{pmatrix} -2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ +2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \\ 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ +2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \\ -R\dot{\phi}^2 \cos \phi - 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \sin \phi - R\ddot{\phi} \sin \phi + \ddot{R} \cos \phi \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\ddot{x} & = -2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \cos \theta - 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\
& + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \sin \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \cos \theta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{i.e., } \ddot{x} & = \left(\ddot{R} - R\dot{\phi}^2 - R\dot{\theta}^2 \right) \sin \phi \cos \theta + \left(R\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \right) \cos \phi \cos \theta \\
& - \left(R\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \right) \sin \phi \sin \theta - 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \sin \theta
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\ddot{y} & = 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta - R\dot{\phi}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta + 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\
& + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R\ddot{\phi} \cos \phi \sin \theta + R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi \cos \theta + \ddot{R} \sin \phi \sin \theta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{i.e., } \ddot{y} & = \left(\ddot{R} - R\dot{\phi}^2 - R\dot{\theta}^2 \right) \sin \phi \sin \theta + \left(R\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \right) \cos \phi \sin \theta \\
& + \left(R\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \right) \sin \phi \cos \theta + 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi \cos \theta
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\ddot{z} = -R\dot{\phi}^2 \cos \phi - 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \sin \phi - R\ddot{\phi} \sin \phi + \ddot{R} \cos \phi$$

$$\text{i.e., } \ddot{z} = \left(\ddot{R} - R\dot{\phi}^2 \right) \cos \phi - \left(R\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} \right) \sin \phi \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_\phi \\ a_\theta \\ a_R \end{pmatrix} = S(\theta, \phi) \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{y} \\ \ddot{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} - R\dot{\theta}^2 \cos \phi \sin \phi \\ R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi + 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi + 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi \\ \ddot{R} - R\dot{\phi}^2 - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin^2 \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_\phi &= R\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{R}\dot{\phi} - R\dot{\theta}^2 \cos \phi \sin \phi \\ a_\theta &= R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi + 2R\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta} \cos \phi + 2\dot{R}\dot{\theta} \sin \phi = R\ddot{\theta} \sin \phi + 2\dot{\theta} \left(R\dot{\phi} \cos \phi + \dot{R} \sin \phi \right) \\ a_R &= \ddot{R} - R\dot{\phi}^2 - R\dot{\theta}^2 \sin^2 \phi \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{e}_\phi a_\phi + \mathbf{e}_\theta a_\theta + \mathbf{e}_R a_R$$

1.1.4 The Two Dimensional Orbit

For a two dimensional orbit we let $\phi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ (constant); and since $r = R \sin \phi$, then $r = R$ and

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \theta \\ r \sin \theta \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} a_\phi = 0 + 0 - 0 \\ a_\theta = r\ddot{\theta} + 0 + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \\ a_r = a_R = \ddot{r} - 0 - r\dot{\theta}^2 \cdot 1 \end{cases}$$

which agrees with the acceleration equations for two dimensional orbits in the x-y (equatorial) plane,

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_r \\ a_\theta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 \\ r\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Reiterating some previously obtained results,

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_r \\ a_\theta \\ a_\phi \end{pmatrix} = Z(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix} = Z(\theta) \cdot Z^{-1}(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 \\ r\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 \\ r\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 \\ r\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = Z^{-1}(\theta) \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 \\ r\ddot{\theta} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\theta} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where

$$Z(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad Z^{-1}(\theta) = Z^T(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

■ End